

D1.6 Two electrode architectures characterized on button-cells

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Executive summary

This deliverable builds on the deliverables D4.1 and D1.4, and reports detailed characterization of several sets of electrodes investigated at button-cell level (both disk-shaped and tubular cells) for different electrode architectures:

- Two $\text{Ba}_{1-x-y}\text{Gd}_x\text{La}_y\text{CoO}_{3-\delta}$ compositions were examined as the steam electrode for reversible steam electrolysis at tubular cell level, showing a significant impact on the electrode composition on overall polarization resistance, particularly when operated in fuel cell mode.
- Two additional electrode systems (PBSCF $\text{PrBa}_{0.5}\text{Sr}_{0.5}\text{Co}_{1.5}\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{O}_{5+\delta}$ and BCFZY: $\text{BaCo}_{0.4}\text{Fe}_{0.4}\text{Zr}_{0.1}\text{Y}_{0.1}\text{O}_{3-\delta}$) were also characterized as potential air electrodes for NH_3 fuel cell operation at tubular cell level, showing comparable and slightly better performance to that of the BGLC-electrodes for reversible operation.
- Porous model electrodes on disk-shaped cells using $\text{Ba}_{1-x}\text{La}_y\text{FeO}_{3-\delta}$ as the standard electrode revealed significant influence of applied bias on the electrode polarization resistance – and non-symmetrical resistance in reversible operation.

For both applications, there is a marked impact of the electrode composition on the electrochemical performance, whereas the overall behaviour of the electrode remains quite similar. In all measurements of the air/steam-electrodes it is apparent that there is an initial increase in the electrode polarization resistance when the cell is operated in fuel cell mode. However, the origin of this increase still remains unclear as it can originate from changes in electronic conductivity of the electrolyte upon applied bias in addition to different kinetics and reaction mechanisms for the oxygen reduction reaction (fuel cell) compared to the oxygen evolution reaction (electrolysis). These results have been corroborated by measurements on porous model electrodes, where also the architecture of the counter electrode have been shown to influence the measurements and subsequent interpretation – and serves as the groundwork for an in-depth study on the effect of electrochemical bias on electrode polarization resistances.

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List of abbreviations

- ASR: area specific resistance
- PCC: electrochemical proton ceramic conducting
- Rp: polarisation resistance
- SOA: State-of-the-art
- EIS: Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy
- OCV: Open Circuit Voltage
- ECM: equivalent circuit models
- MIEC: Mixed ion and electron conductor

Materials

- BGLC: $Ba_{1-x-y}Gd_xLa_yCoO_{3-\delta}$
 - BGLC587: $Ba_{0.5}Gd_{0.8}La_{0.7}Co_2O_6$
 - BGLC37: $Ba_1Gd_{0.3}La_{0.7}Co_2O_6$
- BLC: $Ba_{0.5}La_{0.5}CoO_3$
- BZCY: $BaZr_{1-x-y}Ce_yY_xO_{3-\delta}$
 - BZCY442: $BaZr_{0.4}Ce_{0.4}Y_{0.2}O_{3-\delta}$
 - BZCY81: $BaZr_{0.8}Ce_{0.1}Y_{0.1}O_{3-\delta}$
 - BZCY72: $BaZr_{0.7}Ce_{0.2}Y_{0.1}O_{3-\delta}$
- BZCY81: $BaZr_{0.80}Ce_{0.1}Y_{0.1}O_{3-\delta}$
- PBSCF: $PrBa_{0.5}Sr_{0.5}Co_{1.5}Fe_{0.5}O_{5+6}$
- BCFZY $BaCo_{0.4}Fe_{0.4}Zr_{0.1}Y_{0.1}O_{3-\delta}$

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1 Introduction

1.1 Presentation of WINNER

The WINNER project aims to develop an efficient and durable technology platform based on electrochemical proton conducting ceramic (PCC) cells designed for unlocking a path towards commercially viable production, extraction, purification and compression of hydrogen at small to medium scale. This will be demonstrated in WINNER in three applications: ammonia cracking, dehydrogenation of hydrocarbons, and reversible steam electrolysis. By such, WINNER will create innovative solutions for flexible, secure and profitable storage and utilization of energy in the form of hydrogen and green ammonia, electrification of the chemical industry and sectors coupling.

The WINNER project builds on the pioneering multidisciplinary expertise of world leading partners in the fields of proton conducting ceramic (PCC) materials and technologies to combine materials science, multi-scale multi-physics modelling and advanced in-situ and operando characterization methods to unveil unprecedented performance of tubular PCC cells assembled in a flexible multi-tube module operating at industrially relevant conditions. WINNER will develop innovative cell architectures with multifunctional electrodes and a novel pressure-less current collection system using eco-friendly and scalable manufacturing routes.

Figure 1 WINNER concept focusing on novel materials, electrodes, current collection, and assemblies for three main applications.

The experimental activities will be steered by a novel multi-scale multi-physics modelling platform and enhanced experimentation methodologies. These tools combined with advanced operando and in situ methods will serve at establishing correlations between performance and degradation mechanisms associated with both materials properties and interface's evolution upon operation. Testing of cells and modules will also be conducted to define performance and durability in various operation modes. Techno-economic assessment of the novel PCC processes will be conducted as well as Life Cycle Assessment. The project is coordinated by SINTEF with support from University of

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Oslo, Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior De Investigaciones Cientificas (CSIC-ITQ), Danmarks Tekniske Universitet (DTU), Aktiebolaget Sandvik Materials Technology, CoorsTek Membrane Sciences AS, ENGIE, Shell Global Solutions International B.V.

1.2 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable reports on the electrochemical evaluation of different electrode architectures investigated on disk-shaped and tubular single cells and provides decision support towards developing an innovative electrode architecture for the optimized cells. It builds on the deliverables D4.1 and D1.4, where detailed investigation of electrodes (D4.1) and model electrodes (D1.4) are reported. Herein we present comparative assessments of electrodes tested for two specific applications, namely reversible steam electrolysis and NH_3 -fed proton ceramic fuel cells. In both cases, two different electrode compositions were investigated to identify the impact on electrode performance under open-circuit conditions and in electrochemical operation (with applied bias). In addition, cells with thinner electrolyte layer were also investigated to reveal the extend of the electrolyte contribution to the ohmic loss. In both cases there are several effects observed at a single-cell level that impact the performance under bias, which are not easily understood or rationalized directly from the measurements at tubular cell-level. This is because there are additional contributions from the counter-electrode and the electronic conductivity in the electrolyte that blur interpretations. Thus, a detailed study on the impact of applied electrochemical bias is also presented using porous model electrodes in a three-electrode configuration to dig into the fundamentals of oxide-electrodes under cathodic and anodic bias. In this work, it is observed that the nature and architecture of the counter-electrode plays an important role in the actual DC-behavior of the working electrode. Hence, this deliverable also reports on the effect of counter-electrode architecture on disk shaped cell measurements of porous model electrodes, as a first step towards a deeper fundamental understanding of the electrochemical reactions governing oxide electrodes operated in DC electrochemical bias.

Several electrode/electrolyte compositions are investigated, as reported below. These compositions were intentionally chosen to trigger various contributions from the partial conductivity of each material (e.g. p-type for electrolyte, ionic and electronic in electrode) for the various operating conditions.

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Table 1: List of architectures (electrolyte + electrode) reported in this deliverable

Architecture	Application	Investigation
BLC/BZCY442 / BLC	Model electrode study	Dish shaped samples: influence of the counter electrodes; BLC: mostly proton conducting material.
BLC/ BZCY442 / Pt	Model electrode study	Dish shaped samples: influence of the counter electrodes;
BGLC37/ BZCY442 / Pt	Model electrode study	Dish shaped samples; study on-going. BGLC: protonic and electronic conductor.
BGLC587-BGLC587-BZCY/BZCY81/BZCY-NiO	Reversible steam electrolysis	Improved tubular cell configuration: influence of operational mode
BGLC37-BGLC37-BZCY/BZCY81/BZCY-NiO	Reversible steam electrolysis	Improved tubular cell configuration: influence of operational mode
BGLC587-BZCY/BZCY81/BZCY-NiO	Reversible steam electrolysis	Standard tubular cell configuration: performance in simulated ammonia cracking configuration
PBSCF /BZCY81/BZCY-NiO	NH ₃ fuel cell	New electrode performance in simulated ammonia cracking configuration
BCFZY/BZCY81/BZCY-NiO	NH ₃ fuel cell	New electrode performance in simulated ammonia cracking configuration

2 Comparison of electrode architectures at single tubular cell level

2.1 Reversible steam electrodes on tubular cells

Two different materials in a layered electrode configuration for tubular cells have been compared at SINTEF. The architecture is illustrated in the figure below with the following nomenclature: BZCY/BZCY-BGLC/BGLC. The inner electrode in contact with the electrolyte is a BGLC-BZCY composite on top of which a single-phase layer of BGLC is applied. Each layer is approximately 10µm thick and they have been deposited on standard CTMS half-cells consisting of Ni-BZCY72 electrode and 30±3 µm BZCY81 electrolyte. Here, we will compare this configuration for two different BGLC compositions: BGLC587 (Ba_{0.5}Gd_{0.8}La_{0.7}Co₂O_{6-d}) and BGLC37 (Ba₁Gd_{0.3}La_{0.7}Co₂O_{6-d}). BGLC587 represents the state-of-the-art electrode for steam electrolysis due to its superior stability in very high steam pressures, whereas BGLC37 is a material with higher proton conductivity and faster surface kinetics (demonstrated by surface exchange measurements in collaborative projects) but is shown to partially decompose in 10 bar steam at 600°C after 100 hours (results from FCH JU GAMER project, which we are part of). Whereas the lower stability in steam is problematic for an electrolysis cell operating at high steam pressures, it may not be a significant issue for reversible steam electrolysis where the optimized operating conditions may be at a lower total steam concentration. Furthermore, the analysis and interpretation of the effect of electrode composition will guide further optimization of the steam electrode for a good compromise between stability and performance.

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Figure 2: SEM image(left) of the dual-layered electrode microstructure and a camera picture (right) of the tubular cell after applying silver paste and wire as current collection system.

Figure 3 compared the electrochemical impedance of both electrodes measured in a ProboStat™ setup at 600°C and a total pressure of 3 bar – with 1 bar H₂O and 2 bar air on the steam electrode. As shown in Figure 3, the composite electrode with BGLC37 displays significantly lower polarization resistance than BGLC587 while measured under identical conditions on the same standard tubular half-cell with BZCY81 electrolyte.

Figure 3: EIS spectra of single cells with composite steam electrodes using either BGLC587 (red) and BGLC37 (black). The measurements are done at 600°C and 3 bar total pressure.

Moreover, as reported in deliverable D4.1, the BGLC587 composite electrode displayed a significant increase in polarization resistance in fuel cell mode of operation, causing a significant energy penalty in PCFC mode. This behavior is much less pronounced for the BGLC37 composite electrode, with a minimal increase in electrode polarization resistance when operated at a current of 100 mAcm⁻² in PCFC mode – as depicted in Figure 4. This further illustrates that the BGLC37 composite electrode is

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favorable for reversible operation in terms of electrochemical performance. More in-depth analysis of the electrodes' behavior and performance in reversible operation is already described in D4.1 and D4.3 and will thus not be repeated in this deliverable. The specific mechanisms limiting the overall performance of the BGLC electrodes in fuel cell mode is not yet clear – and remains challenging to identify convincingly from measurements on single tubular cells where there are chemical gradients and the influence of both BGLC electrode and the Ni-BZCY H₂-electrode. Hence, a more fundamental approach using model electrodes on button disk-shaped cells with a three-electrode configuration is needed to directly identify the specific mechanisms when operated at cathodic and anodic bias. This work is reported later in this deliverable.

Figure 4: EIS spectra of BGLC37 (top) and BGLC587 (bottom) composite electrodes on standard tubular cells measured at OCV (black) and 100 mA/cm² (red) at 600°C and 3 bar total pressure.

2.2 Electrodes for NH₃ fuel cell

In addition to the aforementioned BGLC based air electrodes, CTMS has evaluated two well-established air electrodes from literature, PrBa_{0.5}Sr_{0.5}Co_{1.5}Fe_{0.5}O_{5+δ} (PBSCF) and BaCo_{0.4}Fe_{0.4}Zr_{0.1}Y_{0.1}O_{3-δ} (BCFZY), as single-layer electrode configurations with a Ag mesh + Au ink current collector. BCFZY was characterized on standard CTMS tubular half-cell (Ni-BZCY72 electrode with 30±3 μm BZCY81 electrolyte), while PBSCF was characterized on a modified CTMS half-cell with thinner electrolyte (Ni-BZCY72 electrode with 15±2 μm BZCY81 electrolyte). Figure 5 shows Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) spectra at 600 °C and 10 bara total pressure with wet, simulated cracked NH₃ as feed gas and dry air as sweep gas. The electrodes display similar polarization resistances at 600 °C at 10 bara in PCFC mode. The polarization resistances (and ohmic intercept) increase with applied DC bias at small biases, suggested to reflect p-type electronic leakage at OCV (Open Circuit Voltage). At higher biases the intercept remains bias independent while the polarization resistance decreases, and the cells were successfully tested to above 1 A cm⁻² - reflecting that the single layer electrode configuration

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does not limit the electrode performance under high loads. The polarization resistances are furthermore slightly lower than those of BGLC587, particularly under bias, suggesting that these electrodes represent scalable alternatives to BGLC-type electrodes (see D4.1).

The thinner electrolyte adopted for PBSCF has a marginal effect on the ohmic intercept at OCV, and somewhat larger under bias. The intercept improvement is, however, smaller than anticipated from the thickness reduction, suggesting that other factors than electrolyte resistance affect the intercept. This is still under study in WP4.

Figure 5: EIS spectra of (left) PBSCF and (right) BCFZY at OCV (black) and under DC bias up to 256 mA cm⁻² at 600°C and 10 bara total pressure in fuel cell operation. Wet diluted H₂ (i.e. simulated cracked NH₃) was used as feed gas, while dry air was used as sweep gas. The slightly higher p_{H2} adopted for BCFZY is not believed to affect the results due to the minor contribution from the fuel electrode under the adopted conditions. Note that the PBSCF electrode was deposited on a tubular half-cell with a thinner electrolyte (approx. 15 μm), while BCFZY was deposited on a standard CTMS tubular half-cell (approx. 30 μm).

2.3 Preliminary investigation of Ni-electrode in tubular cell configuration

The standard tubular half-cells manufactured at CTMS are exposed to a high temperature sintering step, which gives large NiO particle size in the >10 μm range, and similar Ni particle size after reduction of Ni. Previous electrochemical characterization study gave some indications that the Ni electrode may become limiting under certain conditions. As the work in WP2 entails the development of improved cell architecture, changes in the fabrication procedure are explored to tailor the electrolyte thickness (see above) as well as to tailor the microstructure of the half-cells, by e.g., decreasing sintering temperature, decreasing dwell time at high temperatures. There are also activities on changing reduction conditions, all of which are impacting the Ni electrode microstructure. Examples of these effects are shown in the figure below where changes in the fabrication procedure resulted in changes in the Ni electrode microstructure. The measured cells show lower total ASRs than those measured on standard cells (reduced of about 0.2-0.4 ohm.cm²). Specific electrode polarization resistances revealing the electrode resistance are ongoing.

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Figure 6. Microscopy micrographs of half-cells sintered at different temperatures. All micrographs are given with the same magnification. The Ni grain size decreases with decreasing sintering temperature.

3 Porous model electrodes on disk-shaped cells for fundamental understanding

As impedance measurement under DC bias is challenging, different cell configurations were investigated at UiO to form a reliable base for further studies on model electrodes. Here we first compare the effects of type and size of the counter electrode (CE) on the electrode response of $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{La}_{0.5}\text{CoO}_3$ (BLC) under applied biases, where BLC is an example of an electrode material with high electron and modest proton conductivity. Two counter electrodes are chosen: BLC and Pt. The following configurations of cell systems were studied: BLC/BZCY442 (1%NiO)/Pt and BLC/BZCY442 (1%NiO)/BLC (Figure 7). The BLC/BZCY442 (1%NiO) samples and BLC/BZCY442/BLC were produced with the same manufacturing protocol (see D4.2). The Pt counter electrode was brush painted and annealed in-situ during EIS measurements (also described in D4.1). Figure 8 shows the EIS spectra of both cell systems under wet air at 650 °C. The difference in EIS spectra suggests that type of CE can influence the electrode response. At present, we assign this to differences in microstructure of CE where Pt is more porous than BLC. The second possibility is that Pt and BLC offer difference in relative transport of protons, oxide ions, and electron holes under DC conditions.

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Figure 7: Illustrations showing the configuration and microstructures of BLC electrode surface (darker) with Au current collector (brighter) for BLC/BZCY442/Pt (left) and BLC/BZCY442/BLC (right) cell systems. CE = counter electrode; RE: reference electrode; WE: working electrode.

Figure 8: EIS spectra of BLC/BZCY442/Pt (left) and BLC/BZCY442/BLC (right) cell systems measured at 100 mV (blue), OCV (green), and -100 mV (red) biases at 650°C under wet air.

Figures 8-10 show that both polarisation resistance (R_p) and ohmic resistance decrease with the increase in positive (anodic) bias, and both increase with the increasing negative (cathodic) bias. The change in ohmic resistance is more pronounced in anodic bias when compared to cathodic bias. This indicates diminishing effect of anodic bias on R_p – partly also related to increased p -type conductivity in BZCY442 under positive applied biases.

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Figure 9: EIS spectra of BLC/BZCY442/Pt cell measured under anodic biases (left), and cathodic (right) biases at 650°C under wet air.

Figure 10: EIS spectra of BLC/BZCY442/BLC cell measured under anodic biases (left), and cathodic (right) biases at 650°C under wet air.

Figures 8-11 show the presence of low frequency (LF) inductive impedance loop or semi-circle mainly at higher biases. It is a common phenomenon seen for electrode reactions of Solid Oxide Cells, where the underlying mechanism differs for each specific case and hence considerable discrepancies is seen towards understanding the underlying mechanisms. A typical example of EIS spectra under 100 mV bias fitted with two different equivalent circuit models (ECM) is shown in Fig. 6. This shows the importance of fitting the EIS spectra with correct ECM to better understand the individual electrochemical process and obtain the correct individual and total R_p values. The presence and absence of Gerischer element (G) changes the interpretation of the EIS spectra. Presence and absence of a Gerischer element has been emphasised here because in cases where LF inductor loop is not seen, the impedance data fits perfectly with the use of a Gerischer element in the ECM and it goes with the understanding that Gerischer element is commonly seen for MIEC electrodes. Hence, we further plan to run distribution of relaxation times (DRT) analysis on the experimental data to confirm presence or absence of this element, as DRT is able to deconvolute EIS spectra containing electrochemical processes with similar relaxation times. The other advantage of DRT is that it can be employed without any preconceived notions about number of electrochemical processes. At present, we attribute the LF inductor loop to mass transport process (such as surface adsorption of charged species), which will be further explained and confirmed in the next deliverable.

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Figure 11: EIS spectra of BLC/BZCY442/Pt cell measured under 100 mV bias at 650°C under wet air, showing two different equivalent circuit models (left and right) employed to fit the experimental data (open square).

An important learning point from this study was the observation of a non-reversible effect of the low pO_2 on the electrode performance of BLC/BZCY442/Pt cell system. This is ascribed to a non reversible evolution of the BLC electrode (change of structure) upon exposures to the measurement conditions. We have therefore chosen BGLC materials for the further study of the effect of T , pO_2 and pH_2O under DC biases. $BaGa_{0.3}La_{0.7}Co_{2}O_{6-\delta}$ (BGLC37) is a mixed oxide, electron and proton conductor, and is more stable in reversible operations, as shown in this deliverable. These systems have been prepared, and Figure 12 shows the cell configuration where Ag+BGLC is employed as a counter electrode (CE).

Figure 12: Illustrations showing the configuration and microstructures of working electrode (WE) and counter electrode (CE) for BGLC37/BZCY442/Ag +BGLC cell system. RE: reference electrode.

4 Concluding remarks

This deliverable reports on the development of electrodes for two applications (NH_3 fuel cell and reversible steam electrolysis) and an associated fundamental study on porous model electrodes to elaborate the analysis of electrode reaction mechanisms under electrochemical bias. For both applications there is a marked impact of the electrode composition on the electrochemical

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performance, whereas the overall behaviour of the electrode remains quite similar. In all measurements of the air/steam-electrodes it is apparent that there is an initial increase in the electrode polarization resistance when the cell is operated in fuel cell mode. However, the origin of this increase still remains unclear as it can originate from changes in electronic conductivity of the electrolyte upon applied bias in addition to different kinetics and reaction mechanisms for the oxygen reduction reaction (fuel cell) compared to the oxygen evolution reaction (electrolysis). These results have been corroborated by measurements on porous model electrodes, where also the architecture of the counter electrode have been shown to influence the measurements and subsequent interpretation – and serves as the groundwork for an in-depth study on the effect of electrochemical bias on electrode polarization resistances.